

Mo-CeO₂ Photocatalysts on MICROSCAFS[®]: Defect and Support Engineering for Enhanced CO₂ Photoconversion

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

1. Experimental section

1.1. Photocatalytic CO₂ reduction experiments over the investigated photocatalysts

Photocatalytic CO₂ reduction experiments were carried out in a batch stirred photoreactor (stainless steel, V = 174 ml, Figure 1). The reaction mixture contained 20 ml of 0.2M NaOH with an investigated photocatalyst sample (20 mg) was saturated by CO₂, to purge the air and to saturate the solution. An 8W Hg UVC lamp ($\lambda_{\max} = 254$ nm; Ultra-Violet Products Inc., Upland, USA) was used as the irradiation source and was placed on a quartz glass window in the top of the photoreactor. Subsequently, the photoreactor was closed and before the start of the reaction (switching on the lamp), a gaseous sample was taken through the septum by syringe. The samples of the gaseous phase were analyzed by a GC (gas chromatography, Shimadzu Nexis GC-2030) equipped with BID (barrier discharge ionization detector). The reaction mixture was irradiated for 7 hours and samples were taken at time intervals after 2, 4, 6, and 7 hours for analysis. All of the measurements were reproducibly measured. Three products were detected from the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂: H₂, CH₄, and CO. Two different blank tests were conducted to confirm that the detected products are coming from the

photocatalytic reduction of CO₂. The first blank test was conducted under the same conditions as the photocatalytic reduction itself, except there was no photocatalyst. The second one was carried out with the photocatalyst but without the irradiation. The stability of the investigated sample was demonstrated by repeated use of the same batch with reproducible results.

Figure S1. Image (a) and a scheme (b) of a batch-stirred photocatalytic reactor used for photocatalytic CO₂ reduction experiments.

1.2. Characterization of the investigated photocatalysts

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of the photocatalysts was carried out on powder samples using a PANalytical Empyrean diffractometer (Almelo, Netherlands) operating in reflection geometry, with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) generated at 45 kV and 40 mA. A PIXcel 1D detector was employed to collect the diffracted intensities.

Attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) equipped with a mid-infrared source and diamond ATR optics were applied to study the chemical composition of the samples, using an ATR-FTIR by PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA.

SEM images and EDS elemental analysis of the investigated photocatalyst samples was performed by a scanning electron microscope (Tescan Vega) with tungsten cathode and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS – EDAX).

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out with the 128 channel Argus hemispherical X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (Omicron NanoTechnology) with pass energy 40 eV. The Mg- K α X-ray source was operated at 15 keV, 300 W. XPS measurements were conducted under ultra-high vacuum at room temperature, with pressure below 1.1×10^{-8} mbar. Recorded spectra were processed and deconvoluted with the CASA XPS software package. The Shirley background subtraction and the Gauss-Lorentz curve (GL 30) were used for fitting. Spectra were calibrated to obtain a binding energy of 285.00 eV for C 1s line.

Nitrogen adsorption/desorption analyses were performed at 77 K on an Autosorb 6100 within a relative pressure range (P/P_0) of 0.0016–1.0. the samples were degassed at 100 °C for 24 h before measurement. The specific surface area was obtained by the multipoint BET method, with the optimal linear region selected according to IUPAC/Rouquerol criteria ($R^2 \approx 0.999$).

The diffuse reflectance spectra (DRS) were recorded using a JASCO UV-Vis spectrophotometer equipped with an integrating sphere accessory, and employed to calculate the band gap energies of the samples via the Kubelka-Munk function

Electrochemical measurements were conducted using a photoelectric spectrometer (Instytut Fotonowy, Poland) in a three-electrode configuration. The working electrode consisted of the photocatalyst material, while Ag/AgCl electrode served as the reference electrode, and a platinum wire acted as the counter electrode. A $0.1 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ KNO₃ solution (pH = 6.1) was used as the electrolyte. Prior to measurement, the electrolyte was purged with argon for 15 minutes to remove dissolved oxygen, and a constant argon flow was maintained throughout the experiment. Photocurrents were recorded by front-side irradiation of the working electrode with a 150 W xenon lamp. The wavelength of the incident light was controlled by a monochromator and varied from 250 to 450 nm in 10 nm increments. Voltages ranging from -0.2 to 1.0 V (vs Ag/AgCl) were applied. The irradiated surface area of the

working electrode was 0.785 cm², as determined by the 1.0 cm diameter of the illumination window.

Work function measurements were carried out using a Kelvin probe system (Instytut Fotonowy, Krakow, Poland). This technique is based on measuring the contact potential difference (CPD) between an oscillating reference electrode, made of a gold grid (also referred to as the tip) with a known work function (5.1 eV), and the working electrode (i.e., the sample), whose work function is unknown. The measured CPD corresponds to the difference between the work functions of the tip and the sample (Eq. 1). Consequently, the work function of the sample is calculated using Equation 2.

$$CPD = \Phi_{sample} - \Phi_{tip} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$\Phi_{sample} = CPD + \Phi_{tip} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

During the CPD measurements, the entire system was placed inside a grounded Faraday cage to minimize electrical noise and the influence of stray light. Temperature and humidity within the Faraday cage were monitored throughout the measurement. The work function was measured at a minimum of five different spots on the pellet, and the final value was determined as the average of these measurements.

2. Results and discussion

Figure S2. SEM-EDS images of Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS[®]: (a) elemental distribution map and (b) measured EDS spectra.

Figure S3. Survey XPS spectra of synthesized photocatalysts (a) Mo-CeO₂ and (b) Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS[®]

Figure S4. High-resolution O 1s XPS spectra of (a) CeO₂, (b) MICROSCAFS[®], (c) Mo-CeO₂, and (d) Mo-CeO₂@ MICROSCAFS[®] samples.

Figure S5. DFT pore size distribution and cumulative pore volume for the MICROSCAFS[®] sample.

Figure S6. DFT pore size distribution and cumulative pore volume for the Mo-CeO₂@MICROSCAFS[®] sample.

Table S1. ΔE_{VB} , work function (Φ), and E_{BG} results for the pristine CeO_2 and Mo-CeO_2 samples.

Sample	ΔE_{VB} ^a (eV)	Work function ^b (eV)	E_{BG} (eV)
CeO_2	1.95	5.08 ± 0.04	3.10
Mo-CeO_2	2.05	5.40 ± 0.04	2.90

^a determined by VB-XPS analysis

^b determined by Kelvin probe

Calculation 1 – CeO_2

$$\Phi = 5.08 \text{ eV}$$

$$E_{\text{BG}} = 3.10 \text{ eV}$$

$$\Delta E_{\text{VB}} = 1.95 \text{ eV}$$

1. Fermi level

$$E_{\text{F}} = -\Phi = -5.08 \text{ eV}$$

2. Valence band

$$E_{\text{VB}} = E_{\text{F}} - \Delta E_{\text{VB}}$$

$$E_{\text{VB}} = -5.08 - 1.95 = -7.03 \text{ eV}$$

3. Conduction band

$$E_{\text{CB}} = E_{\text{VB}} + E_{\text{BG}}$$

$$E_{\text{CB}} = -7.03 + 3.10 = -3.93 \text{ eV}$$

4. Conversion to Potential vs. NHE (V)

$$E_{\text{VB}}^{\text{NHE}} = -(-7.03 + 4.44) = 2.59 \text{ V vs. NHE}$$

$$E_{\text{CB}}^{\text{NHE}} = -(-3.93 + 4.44) = -0.51 \text{ V vs. NHE}$$

Calculation 2 – Mo-CeO₂

$$\Phi = 5.40 \text{ eV}$$

$$E_{\text{BG}} = 2.90 \text{ eV}$$

$$\Delta E_{\text{VB}} = 2.05 \text{ eV}$$

1. Fermi level

$$E_{\text{F}} = -\Phi = -5.40 \text{ eV}$$

2. Valence band

$$E_{\text{VB}} = E_{\text{F}} - \Delta E_{\text{VB}}$$

$$E_{\text{VB}} = -5.40 - 2.05 = -7.45 \text{ eV}$$

3. Conduction band

$$E_{\text{CB}} = E_{\text{VB}} + E_{\text{BG}}$$

$$E_{\text{CB}} = -7.45 + 2.90 = -4.55 \text{ eV}$$

4. Conversion to Potential vs. NHE (V)

$$E_{\text{VB}}^{\text{NHE}} = -(-7.45 + 4.44) = 3.01 \text{ V vs. NHE}$$

$$E_{\text{CB}}^{\text{NHE}} = -(-4.55 + 4.44) = 0.11 \text{ V vs. NHE}$$